

Agile research data management with LinkAhead

IndiScale GmbH

History

- LinkAhead started at MPI-DS (Göttingen) around 2011 (name: CaosDB)
- Running stable since ca. 2016, released as open-source (AGPLv3)[1] in 2018
- Increasing adoption since 2020
- Commercial support by IndiScale GmbH
 - distribution branded as LinkAhead

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Challenges: Findability, Linkage, Dynamic Environments

 LinkAhead has:

- Linked data files and meta data.
- Data embedded into original context.
- Easy, yet powerful semantic search.
- Semantic core: Fast and easy tuning of the data model.

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LinkAhead
Thinking Data Management Ahead

Data Life Cycle

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Usability: Automation

- LinkAhead can be automated to free users from the repetitive, error-prone task of inserting data manually.
- Common searches can be stored as templates in LinkAhead.
- We at IndiScale are happy to offer our experience to reduce your work!

Architecture & Crawler LinkAhead

Live-Demo

<https://demo.indiscale.com>

Jupyter Introduction to the CaosDB-Python Client (autosaved)

Data Analysis with Jupyter

```
In [ ]: import caosdb as db
data = db.execute_query("SELECT quality_factor FROM RECORD Analysis with quality_factor")
table = to_table(data)
plt.plot(table.x, table.y)
```


- Online demo:
 - <https://demo.indiscale.com>
- Source code and development: <https://gitlab.com/caosdb>
- Documentation: <https://docs.indiscale.com>
- Scientific article, published in ***Data***:
<https://doi.org/10.3390/data4020083>

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- Integrates into existing workflows
- Stores semantic links together with the data

Thank you for your interest!